

Perceptual Presence as Enactive Inference

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Abstract: I reflect on the notion of lived space and affective resonance as discussed in the target article in the light of the theory of active inference. Interpreting perceptual presence as a form of enactive inference could link the findings presented in the article to a richer theoretical framework that allows for quantitative modelling and neurophenomenological extensions of the present study design. Implementing mutual constraints from complementary neurological or behavioral data could validate or adapt the categories derived in the article.

1. Neurophenomenological methods aim at closing the explanatory gap between phenomenological data of subjective experience in the first-person perspective and neuroscientific or behavioral data from the third-person perspective (Varela 1996). Aleš Oblak, Asena Boyadzhieva, Jure Bon elaborate on the different stages of their study design, which investigates multiple facets of the experience of perceptual presence. While mentioning their neuroscientific inspiration briefly (§13) they leave open what quantitative measures could be used to further evaluate their conclusions. Neurophenomenology envisions to enrich both neurological and phenomenological data by *mutual constraints* between these complementary perspectives (Olivares et al. 2015). Constraining the acquired experiential data with novel neurological data and vice versa would provide a deeper description of the phenodynamic structure of perceptual presence.
2. Even though the authors’ study design is clearly explained and builds on important work in empirical phenomenology, the following question remains unexamined. **How can neuroscientific and behavioral data be integrated to validate the proposed categories of perceptual presence in a quantitative manner? (Q1)** Adding a third-person perspective to the categories derived from the gathered experience samples would reduce the ambiguities involved in coding transcribed data and test the reproducibility of the findings given the small sample size of 8–12 participants (§§14–16). For example, studies on the rubber-hand illusion include measures of skin conductance response and fMRI to investigate the neuronal activity during a period of experiences of agency and ownership of a dummy hand (Limanowski & Blankenburg 2013). Comparing experiential and physiological measures can then be used to correlate brain activity and subjective experience, which would help to identify phenomena that are generalizable to other participants. Given the authors’ expertise with EEG, the design could be similarly extended by a third-person

perspective during the experience of perceptual presence to complement the phenomenological interview data.

3. To derive concrete, quantitative hypotheses from the sampled experiences, computational modelling would additionally be useful to interpret the categories of perceptual presence from an enactive perspective. In their paper “A Tale of Two Densities: Active Inference Is Enactive Inference” Maxwell Ramstead, Michael Kirchhoff and Karl Friston (2020) describe the computational model of active inference as compatible with enactivism and present a possible quantitative description of enactive processes. Oblak and colleagues situate themselves in the enactive perspective. They quote Evan Thompson saying “scientific knowledge of the mind should be based on the direct access we have to the world” (§68), but they miss the opportunity to formulate a computational model and to derive quantitative hypotheses from their findings for follow-up studies. A computational theory of perceptual presence would not only make many implicit assumptions explicit, since computational templates make limitations of scientific theories visible (Humphreys 2002). It would also enable thorough testing of the conclusions drawn from experiential data. Such an iterative application of mutual constraints between neurological and experiential data is what neurophenomenology envisions to close the explanatory gap.
4. The investigation of perceptual presence is a fitting objective for phenomenological interviews, but Oblak and colleagues do not present any explicit hypothesis for follow-up studies that could validate their experiential categories. For example, the derived category of structure of lived space is described as “how space is organized in around an object of perception” (§38). This is further explicated in the sense of Maurice Merleau-Ponty (§39) and leads the authors to find a “solidity of space” as described in phenomenology. By continuously adapting the questions asked in the interview to the participants’ reports, it remains unclear how the authors’ assumptions about what to find in the experiential data construct the categories that have been derived from subjective reports. To avoid circular reasoning in the analysis of the findings it would be helpful to evaluate the significance of the acquired category again in a different task or with a neurological or physiological measure, such as EEG or skin conductance response. Concrete testing of the findings presented in the article could also cast light on how these categories can be generalized to cover a diversity of different people and socio-cultural backgrounds, or if there are specific experiences that are not shared across the participants.
5. Similarly to the structure of lived spaces, the category of affective resonance is presented as a fundamental property of perceptual presence (§56). The notion of affective resonance goes back to Martin Heidegger’s description of presence-as-absence, or the perception of something if the object does not fit the predicted

behavior (§56). From the point-of-view of radical predictive processing and active inference (Clark 2015; Friston et al. 2015), one could reframe this negative description of fundamental experiential processes and think about what role perceptual presence plays in interaction. Instead of claiming that we only consciously perceive things if they do not follow our expectations, active inference enables us to identify this prediction as a prior that helps to plan more complex actions and to develop novel policies. Contrary to presence-as-absence, meditation, mindfulness and other cultural practices demonstrate how perceiving automatic and fully-functioning bodily processes, such as breathing and looking in open awareness, can help us deal with stressful situations without caring about a Heideggerian lack or absence that we must attend to.

6. The points made about the structure of lived space (§38) and affective resonance (§56) show that active inference or related approaches could extend the authors' approach not only from a quantitative perspective but also improve the enactivist interpretation of their findings. This leaves me with the following question: *Do we have to understand the structure of lived space and affective resonance as fundamental properties of subjective experience or can we explain them as priors of the participants constructing the notions in enactive inference? (Q2)*

Acknowledgements

For fruitful discussions about these ideas, I would like to thank Tarja Knuuttila, Andrea Loettgers, Raphael Aybar, Sophie Publig and Julian Bass-Krueger.

Funding

This article is part of a project that has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No 818772).

Competing interests

The author declares that they have no competing interests.

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Received: 8 July 2021

Revised: 10 July 2021